

SUFISM IN ILORIN EMIRATE: A HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

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Abstract

Sufism and Islam are the two sides of the same coin, one of which cannot be divorced from another. The two formed the cornerstone upon which the edifice of Ilorin emirate was built. This was so because, majority of the early scholars who settled at the ancient Okesuna which was the first Islamic centre from which Islam spread to other places in Yorubaland and who propagated Islam and Islamic education within and outside the emirate were Sufis. Suffice it to say that Shaykh Salih bin Junta popularly known as "Shaykh Alimi", whose leadership turned the emirate to a local Makkah was also a Sufi master. In the light of the above, this paper historically examined the establishment of Ilorin emirate and the growth and development of Sufism in it.

Keywords: *Sufism, Ilorin Emirate and Perspective*

Introduction

Sufism, which consists of dedication to the worship of God, Allah, purification of soul from wrong and evil inclinations and abstinence from worldly pleasure, is not an alien practice in Ilorin emirate. From the very beginning, Ilorin scholars who spread both Islam and Islamic education within and outside the emirate were devoted and dedicated adherents of Sufi orders.

Tijaniyyah, the first Sufi order in the emirate, was introduced by the Okesuna scholars while the arrival of Shaykh Alimi ushered in Qadiriyyah. Not long ago, Ikhlesiyyah and Rufaiyyah emerged as Sufi orders.

This write-up, therefore, attempts to examine the beginning and development of each of the above mentioned orders and to uncover some major factors that led to the spread of Sufism in the emirate.

Establishment of Ilorin Emirate

Ilorin emirate comprises of five local government areas namely, Ilorin East, Ilorin South, Ilorin- West, Asa and Moro. It began as a very small village which was founded in 1780 C.E (Al-Ilori, 1982). According to Al-Ilori (1982), the first settler in Ilorin was a Yoruba hunter known as Ojo who came from Ilofa and was later joined by Eminla, Dada and Afonja together with his retinue from Oyo (Al-Ilori, 1982).

Regarding the derivation of the appellation, Ilorin, two major reasons were proffered by historians. The first was the existence of elephants in large number in the town and people referred to it as Ilu erin (town of elephants) which later became "Ilorin" (Al-Ilori, 1986). The existence of a quarter in the town called Oko- erin (the village of elephant) is a convincing evidence which supports this view. The second reason was the existence of a big rock on which the then farmers and hunters used to sharpen their farming and hunting tools respectively. Therefore the name "Ilorin" was taken from 'Ilo' (instrument for sharpening tools) and "Irin" (iron) (Al-Ilori, 1986)

Before the advent of Shaykh "Alimi, the people in Ilorin were the Yorubas whose head was Afonja, the Fulanis Headed by Olufadi, the Hausas and Nupes whose leader was Bako and the people of Oke- suna headed by Solagberu (Jawondo, 2005)

Shaykh Alimi, a great Qadiriyyah Sufi master (Jimoh, 1994) who was born and bred in Tunkara and educated in kebbi town (Al-Ilori, 1982) was invited to Ilorin by Afonja (Jawondo, 2005) and Solagberu because of the piety and efficacy of his prayers, and he was happily received by the people of Ilorin (Al-Ilori, 1986)

The settlement of Alimi in Ilorin attracted many scholars through whose assistance he was able to propagate Islam and Islamic education both within and outside the town. Ajetumobi (2006) states that: "after the arrival of Shaykh Alimi at Ilorin, many muslim scholars were drawn to Ilorin and some of them rendered significant contribution to the growth of Islamic knowledge and dawah in the entire region".

In his own assessment, Abubakare (2006) explains that "Imam Salih Ibn Junta whose epiname is Alimi, a learned man, initiated the unfolding events which turned the city of Ilorin to a de jure and de facto community of saints, of preachers and of scholars."

The Growth and Development of Sufism in Ilorin Emirate

Like Islam, it is not possible for one to state exactly the beginning of Sufism in Ilorin emirate. But what cannot be disproved is the fact that Sufism came into the emirate together with Islam. This is so because, the early scholars of Oke-suna through whom Islam came into the emirate were adherents of Tijaniyyah Sufi order (Jimoh, 1994). Since inception of the emirate till date, four Sufi orders known and practised by its people are Tijaniyyah, Qadiriyyah, Ikhlasiiyyah and Rufa'iiyyah. Each of these orders is succinctly examined as follows:

Tijaniyyah Order: This Sufi order was founded by Abul- Abbas, Shaykh Ahmad bin Muhammad bin Mukhtar At- Tijani who was born in Ayn-Mad in Morocco in 1737 C.E and died in 1815 C.E (Solagberu, 2000). He was blessed with supernatural intelligence and was able to memorize the Holy Qur'an at the age of seven (Alli, 2001). He was famous for his piety, knowledge, respect, simplicity, love for God and devotion to His worship. Tijaniyyah order has teeming adherents in many countries of the world, especially in North and West Africa (Solagberu, 2000).

Tijaniyyah was the first Sufi order Ilorin people had contact with and practised even before the arrival of Shaykh Alimi. Jimoh (1994) explains:

The Tijaniyya is the oldest tariqa in Ilorin. It was first introduced in ilorin by Kanuri scholars who formed the cream of Muslim leaders in the ancient Okesuna quarters built by Solagberu. The Tijaniyya was already well established in Okesuna before the arrival of Shehu Alimi. Solagberu (Abdullahi Tahir) the head of that Okesuna community and his followers belonged to the Tijaniyya (Jimoh, 1994).

Tijaniyyah was flourishing until there was an outbreak of war between Solagberu, the leader of the Tijanis and AbdulSalam, the then Emir of Ilorin who belonged to Qadiriyyah order. The rift eventually led to the destruction of Okesuna and the execution of Solagberu (Jimoh, 1994). This ugly occurrence caused a setback to Tijaniyyah as many adherents completely abandoned it while others who did not abandon it were practising it secretly for fear of being attacked by the Emir's soldiers. The Qadiriyyah took advantage of the incident and became the dominant group (Jimoh, 1994).

The obscurity of Tijaniyyah group persisted until an Ilorin scholar known as Mallam Muhammad Wali of Ita Kudima area re-introduced the order in the town. But the man was not given freedom to practise the rites of the Tariqah and was also subjected to severe torture by the then Emir of Ilorin, 'Ali (1869-1891) who was also a member of Qadiriyyah (Quadri, 1983).

The Tijaniyyah regained its freedom and strength in 1900 when the first ZAWIYA was built at Pakata by Alfa AbdulSalam who was popularly called Baba Arugbo and who died in 1942 C.E. The man was said to have been initiated into the order in Cairo, Egypt while he was returning from Makkah where he performed the Hajj (Jimoh, 1994).

The concerted efforts made by AbdulSalam and his disciples such as Muqaddam Bashir Adangba who built the second ZAWIYAH in Ilorin in 1918, Al- hajj Nda Rabi of Karuma in Gambari area, Al-hajj Abubakar Alore, Muqaddam Sa'adu Balogun Ajikobi and Muqaddam Ode Ikokoro among many others led to the quick spread of the Tijaniyyah order in Ilorin (Solagberu, 2000).

Qadiriyyah Order: This was founded by Shaykh Abdul- Qadir bin Abdullahi Al- Jaylani who was born in Jilan, a village in Persia in 1077 A.D. and died in 1166 A.D (Alli, 2001). He was known as pious and devoted scholar. His order is practised in many countries in Africa and beyond. Also, it is the oldest Sufi order in Nigeria (Solagberu, 2000).

Qadiriyyah was said to have been introduced in Ilorin by Shaykh Alimi on his arrival in the town in the early years of the nineteenth (19th) century (Jimoh, 1994). Shaykh Alimi's piety, knowledge, spiritual elevation among other good qualities attracted people of Ilorin to the Qadiriyyah. Therefore, the order flourished very rapidly. In addition, with the destruction of Okesuna and execution of Solagberu, the Tijaniyyah leader could not be underrated among the factors that contributed to the quick spread of the Qadiriyyah.

Other than Shaykh Alimi and his descendants, others who contributed to the spread of Qadiriyyah in Ilorin were Shaykh Bukhari, Shaykh Khalil (Alfa Gbodofu), Shaykh Abubakar Bube, Mallam Dogo (the first Imam Gambari of Ilorin), Shaykh Ibrahim popularly called "Qumburin Karatu" (Grave of learning), Shaykh Takhati an- Nafawi, Shaykh Tajul- Adab, Alfa Belgore, Alfa Omo Ikokoro, Alfa Salisu Kokewu Kobere and Alfa Erubu (Solagberu, 2000).

The contribution of Shaykh Ahmad Rufai Nda Salati to the spread of Qadiriyyah can never be overemphasised. He introduced the recitation of litanies congregationally in public, established a Zawiyah in front of his house and authorized his disciples to establish Zawiyahs in their various houses (Solagberu, 2000).

Ikhlasiiyyah Order: Unlike Tijaniyyah and Qadiriyyah which are of foreign origin, *Ikhlasiiyyah* was established by an Ilorin scholar, Shaykh Muhammad Bashir Olorundare bin Shaykh Suleman Obayayi bin Abdul-Qadir bin Abdullahi Bashir Olorundare bin Shaykh Suleman Obayayi bin Abdul-Qadir bin Abdullahi bin Ibrahim bin Muhammad Sanusi bin Abdulwahab bin Muhammad Nasir Ilory (Adua, 2007). Shaykh Olorundare was born in 1936 C.E. Four years after his birth, his mother died and he was brought up by his aunt called Hawwau. His paternal lineage is traceable to Oyo while his maternal to Fulanis (Adua, 2007). He began his Quranic education from Mualim Saad at idi- ayunre, Okelele, Ilorin before traveling to Ogbomoso with his aunt where he spent three years learning from different scholars like Alhaji Badrudeen of Alabo, oke- elerin and others (Adua, 2007). As a trader, his father used to travel a lot and took him along wherever he went. Through this, he developed the habit of traveling and making friendship with different people of different social, religious, political and educational background.

When he attained puberty, he gained total independence from his father and started traveling to different countries of Africa and other continents. He visited Morocco, Azhar (Cairo), India, Britain, Libya, Mali, Rwanda, Congo etc to study and acquire certificates in Science, Astronomy and Mathematics. He returned to Nigeria in 1964 and got married in 1966 (Adua, 2007).

In addition to his being a Sufi master, he was a prolific writer whose books among others include:

- * The Hidden key of magical act (1967)
- * Ar- Rahmah Al- kubrah (1979)
- * Tarikh At- Turq Ad- Diniyyah Mundh fajr Al- Hijrah (1983)
- * Al- 'Ibadah Fi Al- Islam (1987)

* Ad- Din wa al- 'Aql wa Al- Falsafah wa Al- 'Alaqah Baynaha (1989) (Adua, 2007)

As a devoted servant of God, he engaged in seclusion, meditation, fasting and worship till he became spiritually empowered. Hence, he established his order (Ikhlasiiyyah) in 1972 (Adua, 2007).

Since inception till date, the order is practised in Ilorin and some places like Ibadan, Abeokuta and Lagos. Moreover, some Ikhlasiiyyah spiritual centres (Zawiyahs) are located at Kuntu, Agaka, Olosun compound, Sawmill area, Alabere compound and Okelele with quite appreciable number of adherents (Solagberu, 2000).

Rufa'iyah Order

Shaykh Ahmad Rufa'i bin Abul Abbas who was born in 1106 and died in 1183 was said to have originated the Sufi order popularly referred to as "Rufaiyyah" (Solagberu, 2000). The appellation was derived from the founder's name "Rufai". This Sufi order is very recent in Ilorin emirate. It was introduced in 1994 by Shaykh Fasasi Ahmad of Isale-koto, Ilorin who was initiated into the order while he was a student in Cairo, Egypt (Solagberu, 2000).

About four years after its introduction, the order was brought into the limelight through her maiden annual Mawlid Nabiyy celebration organized by its flag bearer in 1998. In the following year, a more elaborate occasion was organized and graced by eminent Sufi Shaykhs of different orders (Solagberu, 2000). The only Zawiyah of the order is located at Isale Koto in Ilorin (Solagberu, 2000).

Factors that led to the spread of Sufism in ilorin Emirate.

Sufism spread rapidly in Ilorin emirate due to a number of factors among which are the following:

(i) **The visit of Shaykh Ibrahim Niyas to the emirate:** Shaykh Niyas was regarded as the world leader of Tijaniyyah order during his lifetime. On 11th November, 1963, he visited Ilorin town and was warmly received by eminent Tijaniyyah Shayks and adherents including the then Emir of the emirate, Alhaji Dhul- Qurnayn Gambari (Alli, 2001). Shaykhs Abubakar Salaudeen Agbarigidoma and Folohunsho Fagba were said to have been among the scholars who composed eulogies as part of welcome package (Solagberu, 2000). The Ansarul Islam Society of Nigeria under the leadership of Shaykh (Dr.) Muhammad Kamaldeen Al- Adabiyy also organized a befitting reception in honour of Shaykh Niyas (Solagberu, 2000).

Fascinated by Niyas' exemplary and extra- ordinary qualities, countless people sought initiation into Tijaniyyah order. Therefore, since the period of visit to date, there has been a cordial relationship between the Tijanis in the emirate and Niyas' descendants. In fact, on yearly basis, many Tijanis in the emirate go (in groups) to Kawlakh in Senegal to celebrate MAWLID (the birth of prophet Muhammad) and to pay homage and allegiance to Shaykh's family.

(ii) **The efficacy of Sufis' prayers**

Miracles performed by some Sufi scholars in the emirate can never be underestimated among the factors that led to the spread of Sufism. For example, Alfa Eleha used to cure many diseases which other healing homes had considered incurable. He used to pray for people once in a year in his house and whatever people requested would be granted. Quadri (1983) adds:

This was considered by the people as Karamah which he acquired by his being a member of the Tijaniyyah and this made many people join the tariqah with the aim of acquiring such power.

(iii) Mawlid Nabiyy Celebration:

The practice of celebrating the birth of prophet Muhammad every year which Shaykh Ibrahim Niyas of Kawlakh was known for, was copied by many Sufi Shaykhs and Muqaddams of all Sufi orders and that has greatly contributed to the wide spread of Sufism in the emirate.

(iv) The role of Shaykh Nuru- Hakeem.

Shaykh Nuru-Hakeem (d.2011) was one of the Tijaniyyah Shayks blessed with excessive mystical knowledge and high spiritual attainment. He was able to demystify, defend and justify Sufi teachings and practices through his lectures which used to attract large audience from within and outside the emirate. Solagberu corroborates this saying:

The coming of Shaykh Nuru Hakim to Ilorin in 1960s served as a stimulus for the development of Tijaniyyah in the town and its environs, for he publicly interprets Qur'an mystically, an act which created mixed feelings among the people (Solagberu, 2000).

Conclusion

In this paper, an attempt has been made to provide a succinct historical survey of the establishment of Ilorin emirate and the development of Sufism in it. Since inception till date, only four Sufi orders namely; Tijaniyyah, Qadiriyyah, Ikhlasiiyyah and Rufayyah are known and practised by the people of the emirate. In addition, the visit of Shaykh Ibrahim Niyas of Kawlakh, the efficacy of the Sufis' prayers, the annual celebration of the prophet's birthday and the role of Shaykh Nuru- Hakeem were identified as the major factors that contributed to the wide spread of Sufism in Ilorin emirate.

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